

RADIANT-CREATOR

“Woody Crops”

Workshop

16th – 18th February,
Castellón (Valencian Region, Spain)

Hosted by CONNECTA NATURA
(a Non-Governmental Organisation)

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Executive Summary

This CREATOR workshop showcased traditional crop varieties from the Iberian Peninsula, focusing on how traditional woody crops and woody crop products can be brought to farmers' fields and consumers' tables. The workshop centred around the question: *what are the possibilities and challenges posed by this endeavour, and as an adaptive response to the climatic and socioeconomic crisis that Mediterranean agriculture is facing?*

A diverse range of stakeholders gathered to discuss the opportunities and obstacles for producers and consumers to adopt traditional woody crops. This was achieved through a complex program with various showcases, specific participatory learning activities, tastings, and round table discussions which took place in Castellón city centre.

Activities specifically designed to attract members of the public with no previous knowledge or awareness of traditional woody crops were also included, such as free-play activities for children and a local products market showcasing 10 different projects from Castellón rural areas.

This event also provided a platform for 17 speakers from different projects across the whole Iberian Peninsula, to direct discussions and exchange ideas, and more than 80 participants were involved including stakeholders from across the value chains such as local authority decision makers, researchers, food producers, retailers, and consumers.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background and objectives

Mediterranean agriculture has been in an acute crisis for years because of climate change and extreme weather stochasticity (including droughts, extreme temperatures, increase in pests and diseases), and exacerbated by the socio-economic crisis and impacts of the species-limited, linear, industrialised and/or globalised agri-food markets. This crisis is impacting negatively on traditional cultivation, culture, and markets for hegemonic woody crops of the Mediterranean region; and specifically for trees such as citrus, olive, and almond, among others. Hence, it becomes increasingly difficult to make a living from these crops, especially in dry and mountainous regions.

Several studies (FAO, 2010) indicate that one solution to alleviate this crisis could be through the diversification of production and the recovery of species and varieties that have been traditionally cultivated in the territory; and which are more adapted to the local conditions and hence more resilient to changes in climate. Applying current knowledge and technical resources to these crops can improve their productivity and achieve more sustainable crop and food systems compared to conventional agriculture. In addition, the transformation of by-products adds value to their cultivation, expanding consumption and other commercialisation channels. Finally, it is important to remember that the traditional crops also offer other added adaptive values compared to conventional standard crop - owing to their biophysical suitabilities which render them more suitable for certain landscapes and linked cultures.

It is also necessary to consider the impacts of a globalised production driven agri-food system, where profitability of multinational enterprises is optimised through market control while income protection and production environment protections for farmers, and especially smallholder producers, is not safeguarded and has declined into non-profitability. It therefore has been necessary for producers to regain control of value chain capacities both horizontally and vertically (i.e., input usages including which crops and varieties are cultivated, processed, distributed, and retailed), to gradually add and retain value to the product, and foster better relationships with consumers, and

better safeguard biodiversity environmental functions. That is, there is unprecedented need to move towards short 'dynamic value chains', diverse, adaptable, and resilient, with a closer links to consumers.

In addition, the recently published European Union's Agricultural Outlook Report, concluded that the increase in consumers' concern for their health, animal welfare and the environment will require EU farmers to produce a greater diversity of crops and establish more direct links with consumers. We must move towards greater agrodiversity, plus more sustainable and equitable models of production and consumption, which place greater value on land use and ecological functions, plus the wellbeing at of citizens.

The RADIANT project integrates these two perspectives to develop participatory research approaches aimed at co-generating knowledge, and tools that favour the transition towards agrobiodiverse production which sees producers and consumers directly connected, and mutually aware. To promote this change, the RADIANT project studies traditional crops from an agronomic, environmental, economic, and social perspectives, assessing different value chains models for underutilised crops where production, transformation, and distribution are innovative and may be practically implemented by producers, especially those on low incomes. Connecta Natura is one of 28 RADIANT project partners which include research centres, universities, commercial entities, and non-profit (community interest) companies from across Europe.

As part of this project, CREATOR workshops are organised, and here to introduce the various traditional woody crops of the Iberian Peninsula; and to explore and elaborate options to realise options to ensure they continue to be cultivated and appreciated by farmers and consumers. Thus, under the theme of "Root Regrowth", this event brought together farmers, consumers, and experts at the Espai Cultural El Menador in Castelló, on the 17th and 18th February 2023, to discuss the opportunities and challenges in recovering the use of traditional woody crops to help reverse the economic and climate crisis that Mediterranean agriculture is currently experiencing.

1.2 Workshop framework and participants

During the three days of the event around 200 adults and 50 children attended the different activities carried at this Woody Crops CREATOR workshop. More specifically: 61 people attended the field visit, presentations, and workshops in the Menador, and around 150 adults and 50 children attended the market of local products.

Table 1. Number of participants attending the different activities organised during the Woody Crops CREATOR workshop.

Day	Activity	
16 th	Field visit for RADIANT partners	8
	Presentations – projects and initiatives related with traditional woody crops	33
17 th	Networking for traditional woody crops	27
	Showcases – grafting workshop	35
	Farmers' and consumers' focus groups	35
	Local products and RADIANT products tasting event	30
	Round table discussion on Consumption and Production Experiences	42
18 th	Round table discussion on Experiences in the Recovery of Woody Crops	41
	Closing group dynamics	25

In terms of stakeholders attending the activities carried out in the Menador and the field visit, 40% were professional and non-professional producers, 25% consumers, 17% people belonging to social movements, 13% academics, and 5% policy makers (Figure 1).

Stakeholders

Figure 1. Stakeholders who attended the activities organised during the Woody Crops CREATOR workshop.

2. Presentations

2.1 Presentations Overview

These two sessions were organised to focus on operational aspects which aim to release the full value of underutilised and genetically diverse woody crops; making them more competitive and supportive of EU policies for sustainable agrifood chains. Also, to foster synergies more-positive synergies among all food chain actors, and for the benefit of local agricultural production, biodiversity, and the delivery of other ecosystem services (or functions) regionally, and with global relevance. Towards this goal, the RADIANT project comprises 45 case studies, named AURORA's (many of which are farms, though not all), promoting different aspects necessary for well-functioning underutilised crop value chains.

As part of this event, Connecta Natura from Castelló de la Plana organised interactive knowledge-exchange sessions on the, "*recovery of traditional woody crops for agriculture with a future*". In terms of fruit trees, the genotypes and specific agronomic methods are a valuable heritage whose preservation is urgently required. Therefore, the presentations were organised in two distinct sessions. The first session on Friday 17th February was aimed at the public internationally and held in English. The second session on Saturday 18th February, was aimed at the Spanish public, and was held in both Spanish and Catalan. These presentation sessions were also structured around three thematic Round Table discussions where speakers were able to converse and exchanged ideas with both their peers, and the public attendees.

All the presentations were streamed live on the CONAT Youtube Channel and are freely available online: [@connectanatura](#). Photographs taken during the session are also available [here](#).

2.2 Friday 17th Dissemination Session

Friday February 17th from 9:30 a.m. to 12 p.m. → **Presentations of international projects related to the recovery of traditional woody crops.**

- Link: <https://youtube.com/live/TUHh7MLs7Do?feature=share>

Itinerary

Introduction

- Presentation of the event: Connecta Natura
- RADIANT Project: Marta Vasconcelos - RADIANT Coordinator
- Traditional crop varieties and traditional woody crops of the Iberian Peninsula: Connecta Natura

Presentations

- **Connecta Natura:** Pau Agost Andreu - Participatory recovery of traditional fruit varieties of the regions of Castellón.
- **Varieties and Agricultural Knowledge Guardians Network:** Dorian - Participatory network for the recovery of crops and traditional agricultural knowledge of the regions from Castello.
- **La Troje Association:** Laura Aceituno - Recovery, participatory study and promotion of traditional fruit varieties of the Sierra de Madrid.
- **Euskal Herriko Haziien Sarea (Basque Seed Network):** Violeta Furlan - Recovery, participatory study, and promotion of traditional fruit varieties in the Basque Country.
- **Freixo do Meio:** Ana Fonseca - Agroforestry farm. Acorns, Jujubes, and other wild woody farming.
- **Laura Palau:** Promoting the recovery and consumption of traditional woody crops through art.

2.3 Saturday 18th dissemination session

Saturday February 18th from 10 a.m. to 12 p.m. → **Round table discussion on experiences of Consumption, Elaboration, Production and Distribution.**

- Link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Yn18KAQHxbs>

Consumer's Round Table Speakers

- **Som alimentació Consumers Cooperative** (Valencia)
- Lluís Castellà.
- **La Maraña Consumers Group** (Benicassim) - Josev

Production and distribution Round Table Speakers

- **Arbolè** - Efrén Martín Martín - Traditional fruit tree varieties trees nursery
- **Freixo do Meio** - Alfredo - Agroforestry farm. Cultivation of Acorns, Jujubes and other wild woody
- **Terra i Xufa** - Enric Navarro - Production and distribution of organic vegetables and fruits in the Valencian region.

Saturday February 18th - 12:40 p.m. - 2:20 p.m. → **Round table on experiences in the recovery of traditional crop varieties.**

- Link: <https://youtube.com/live/7TqIkeUYSYQ?feature=share>

Round Table Speakers

- **FENT y Red de Semillas (Spanish seed Network)** - Maria Carrascosa - Current political and legislative context of agrobiodiversity.
- **Asociación Albar** - Cesareo - Recovery and promotion of traditional varieties from the Rincón de Ademuz region.
- **Asociación para el Desarrollo Rural Comarcal de la Hoya de Huesca** - Javier - Recovery and promotion of traditional fruit varieties in Huesca region.
- **Euskal Herriko Haziaren Sarea (Red de semillas de Euskadi)** - Joseba Ibargirengoitia Gasco - Recovery and promotion of

traditional fruit varieties and chestnut cultivation in the Basque Country. Citizen participation and opportunities in the current legislative context.

During Saturday sessions, a graphic artist and facilitator collected the main ideas of each presentation in the form of a mural, elaborating one mural per round table. All the speakers and the participants were then invited to interact with these murals and discuss the topics explored throughout the morning. The three murals designed during the session are shown below as a result of graphic collection and interactions.

Consumer's Round Table Mural

Production and distribution Round Table Mural

Experiences in the recovery of traditional crop varieties Round Table Mural

3. Demonstration activity / Field visit

3.1 Field Visit

The visit to Connecta Natura's field site started by a visit of CONAT's Traditional Fruit Tree Varieties Collection, and agricultural and forestry plots managed by CONAT at Xinquér Valley (Alcudia de Veo, Castellón, Valencian Region) located at the heart of the Sierra de Espadán Natural Park.

At the Traditional Fruit Tree Varieties Collection, attendees witnessed a collection of genotypes which require urgent conservation, and the compilation and revaluation of the traditional knowledge associated with their cultivation and cultural significance. In addition, CONAT outlined the work undertaken since 2019 to recover and promote these traditional woody crop varieties, as a critical re-diversification measure for such crops in the rural areas; also, as a vehicle to promote the uptake of agroecological approaches in the region. Participants also visited other agricultural and forestry plots also managed with an agroecological approaches by CONAT at Xinquér Valley. This was followed by a tasting event of local products based on, or related to, underutilised traditional crop varieties from the region.

After lunch, participants visited CONAT's Tree Nursery located in Vall d'Alba (Castellón), where CONAT is multiplying traditional fruit tree varieties using resilient ecology-based methods. During the visit, CONAT explained the procedures used for the multiplication and management of the traditional fruit tree varieties.

The field visit ended with a social mixer and a dinner in Pou de Beca (<https://poudebeca.com/es/>), a local restaurant specialised in the use of local and traditional products.

3.2 Grafting Workshop

A 'grafting workshop' was also organised, in both English and Spanish, on Friday 17th from 15:15 to 16:15. The workshop was also streamed live through the CONAT YouTube Channel and now is available online: [Jornades Rebrots d'Arrel - Taller d'Empelts - Cultius llenyosos tradicionals.](#)

This workshop was designed to introduce participants to the main principles of grafting, and basic technical information to understand what a graft is, how it works, and why it can succeed or fail. After this technical introduction, two grafting techniques were showcased live with a full explanation provided of the methodology.

3.3 Traditional Fruit Trees Distribution

During the event, traditional fruit trees recovered and grafted by CONAT were distributed among amateur and professional farmers participating in the participatory study and preservation network included in RADIANT Project.

In total, 55 fruit trees were distributed among 5 non-professional farmers, 1 professional farmer, and 1 High School where agroecology is taught albeit in a limited manner.

3.4 Local products and agroecological market

Date: Saturday, 18th February from 10:00 a.m. to 2:00 p.m. and from 4:30 p.m. to 8:00 p.m.

The local products and agroecological market, supported by the Castelló City Council, was a great success with a large number of people attending from across the region. Approximately 150 people visited the market throughout the day, and were able to buy, taste and learn about the excellent quality of the products of the region. All products

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including oils, vegan almond pâtés, carob chocolate, wines, artisan vermouths, shepherd's cheeses, homemade jams, honey were all made from different parts of the Castellón region and represented the efforts of small producers to offer healthy, artisanal, and local food to the public. In addition, product samples were available at each stand so participants could taste and appreciate the quality of the products showcased. The market featured nine producer's stalls, a rural products retailer of products from other various agroecological producers, and two information stalls – one on traditional crop varieties, and the other agroecology.

In addition, specific activities aimed at children were organised to promote participation and ensure opportunities for all participants to learn about traditional crop varieties. These activities were thoroughly planned to highlight what constitutes agroecology and agroecological approaches, and the importance of preserving biodiversity at a level to be understood and appreciated by children.

In total, around 50 children attended on Friday and Saturday, all of whom appeared to enjoy and learn from the activities which were offered.

4. Outputs of discussions

4.1 Summary

During this CREATOR event, two breakout sessions were organised. The first session was a “Group Dynamics and World Cafe” in which participants met, networked, and discussed the main issues related to the production and consumption of underutilised woody crops and heirloom varieties. To this end, the world café approach was followed. The second session was a “Farmers and consumers focus group” to explore the attributes that can favour the consumption and cultivation of traditional crop varieties, using the traditional crop variety “Tomaca de penjar de Benlloc” as a case study. The main aim of this session was to identify economic, social, policy, and other barriers and opportunities related to the consumption of underutilised crops. To this end, producers and consumers filled “choice cards” describing tomatoes through different characteristics which they were asked to choose from. The cards aimed to explore their views, attitudes, and opinions on consuming and cultivating Tomaca de penjar de Benlloc. Then, they were asked to participate in two group discussions. The first discussion aimed to evaluate their understanding of the questionnaire, and the second discussion explored their opinions on issues related to the adoption of underutilized crops.

4.2 Breakout sessions

A. Group Dynamics and World Cafe

17th February from 12:30 to 14:00

The aim of this specific session was to meet, network and discuss as a group underutilised woody crops and heirloom varieties.

First, participants were sat in a circle and asked to introduce themselves in terms of their name and origin, their favourite heirloom variety and finally imitate a sound from nature that they liked. All participants then had to imitate it.

The world café approach was then used to discuss the main issues related to the production and consumption of underutilised woody crops and heirloom varieties. Details of the contents of the four tables are summarised below.

1. Negative aspects and perceived obstacles to implementation of underutilised woody crops in production.

- Do not produce traditional products only for rich people
- Hard to produce (lack of know-how: uncertainties regarding production)
- Hard conditions of work for farmers
- No transfer of traditional knowledge
- No easy way to identify and register old varieties
- No incentives, no real political agenda
- Lack of regulation for use of traditional varieties
- Access to local varieties
- Hidden value of agriculture
- Hard to sell to consumers, buyers (unusual)
- Lack of awareness of the wider public
- Lack of knowledge about the resources and varieties farmers have in their farms
- The agriculture is not profitable
- Lower yields from local variety

2. Motivations and collective challenges to implementation of underutilised woody crops in production.

- Motivations
 - Rusticity, low input requirements and local adaption
 - Conventional model problems
 - Improve the landscape and the environment
 - Their great diversity can provide trade opportunities, serve as insurance against climate change and increase seasonal food (harvest and post-harvest).
- Collective challenges
 - Participatory research
 - Organisation and network production
 - Urban farming
 - Landscape and environmental improvement
 - Promotion of the associated cultural heritage

- Farmers formation: workshops, visits, farmer to farmer programs, reference project

3. Promotion of underutilised woody crops in consumption including transformation, distribution and research

- Slow food alliance -> link consumers to producers
- Food fair events, taste of products (schools), media promotion - > people need to know
- Civic awards prizes for producers
- Present local varieties properties
- Cookbooks on sale in local and urban outlets, show cooking, cooking TV programs (celebrity chefs)
- Do not copy the conventional market system:
 - promote local markets, local networks of producers-consumers
 - cooperatives, ampas (farmers supported by families)
- Research how local varieties can be used or transformed. Tech for small scale projects
- Index of heirloom varieties, public seed catalogue
- Government influence in:
 - schools, hospitals
 - producing facilities
 - public contracts

4. European political and legislative framework. Difficulties, opportunities, prospects for change and action strategies

- Negative points:
 - heirloom varieties are difficult to register because they do not meet regulatory criteria (e.g., uniformity).
 - selling unregistered varieties risks fines
 - it is difficult to demonstrate or quantify the value of local varieties.
 - risk of private appropriation by companies or lobbies
- Positive points:
 - participatory variety catalogues
 - genetic labelling recording methodology. Easier now
 - relaxation of regulations
 - promotion through public food procurement

B. Farmers' and consumers' focus groups

17th February from 17:00 to 19:00

The Farmers and consumers focus groups were designed by the James Hutton Institute and Connecta Natura to explore the attributes that can favor the consumption and cultivation of traditional crop varieties. The main aim was to identify economic, social, policy, as well as other barriers and opportunities related to the consumption of underutilised crops.

The workshop was held in parallel for producers and consumers, using the traditional crop variety “Tomaca de penjar de Benlloc” (Benlloc hanging tomato) as a case study. Firstly, producers and consumers were asked questions on their socio-demographics, consumption characteristics and attitudes.

Secondly, they were asked to fill in “choice cards” describing tomatoes through a series of different characteristics which they were asked to choose from. The cards aimed to explore their views, attitudes, and opinions on consuming and cultivating Tomaca de penjar de Benlloc. The results of the choice experiment will help us understand which characteristics matter the most when deciding which tomatoes to consume and cultivate.

Participants were then asked to participate in two group discussions. The first aimed at evaluating their understanding of the experiment, both in terms of language and content, whilst the second explored their opinions on issues related to the adoption of underutilized crops. More specifically, these participatory activities analysed the strengths,

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weaknesses, opportunities or threats that arise when growing underutilized crops.

At the end of the experiment, participants were asked to repeat the choice card exercise.

